

Section 1: PowerPoints

PowerPoints for February 11-12, 2020 "Advanced Analytics for CW Administration Data Slam"

PDF Building Capacity DS.2020 Download View

PDF Using Evidence to Build Narrative DS.2020 Download View

PDF Plan Do Study Act DS.2020 Download View

Introduction to Advanced Analytics in Tableau

Advanced analytics in Tableau is a powerful approach to uncovering insights from data, enabling organizations to make data-driven decisions. By leveraging advanced features and functionalities, Tableau provides a comprehensive solution for analyzing complex data sets.

Section 2: Exercises and Agenda

Exercises and Agenda for February 11-12, 2020 "Advanced Analytics for CW Administration Data Slam"

PDF 1.DS.2020.Name The Population Download View

PDF 2.DS.2020.CoreOutcome: Download View

PDF 3.DS.2020.AskingAnswering Download View

PDF Data Slam Agenda

PDF 1.DS.2020.Name The Population Download View

PDF 2.DS.2020.CoreOutcomes Download View

PDF 3.DS.2020.AskingAnswering Download View

PDF Building Capacity DS.2020 Download View

PDF Data Slam Agenda Download View

PDF Plan Do Study Act DS.2020 Download View

PDF Using Evidence to Build Narrative DS.2020 Download View

Overview of Tableau Software

Tableau is a leading data visualization and business intelligence software that empowers users to create interactive and shareable dashboards. It offers a user-friendly interface, seamless integration with various data sources, and robust tools for data exploration and visualization.

One of the key strengths of Tableau is its ability to simplify complex data into easily understandable visualizations.

Exploring Data Visualization Techniques

Data visualization techniques play a crucial role in advanced analytics. Tableau provides a wide range of visualization options, including bar charts, line graphs, heat maps, and more. These techniques allow users to effectively communicate insights and trends hidden within the data.

1

Interactive Dashboards

Tableau enables the creation of interactive dashboards, which allow users to explore data and gain insights through dynamic visualizations.

2

Custom Visualizations

Users can build custom visualizations to represent data in unique and insightful ways, providing deeper understanding and analysis.

3

Storytelling with Data

Tableau offers storytelling features, allowing users to create narratives using data, thereby enhancing the impact of data analysis.

Understanding Data Blending and Data Modeling

Data blending in Tableau involves combining data from multiple sources to gain comprehensive insights. It allows users to integrate and visualize diverse data sets to uncover correlations and patterns. Furthermore, data modeling enables the creation of relationships between data for more complex analyses.

Applying Advanced Statistical Analysis in Tableau

Tableau enables advanced statistical analysis through its integration with statistical tools, such as R and Python. This facilitates the application of predictive analytics, clustering, and regression analysis to derive deeper insights from data.

Predictive Analytics

Tableau provides predictive modeling capabilities, allowing users to forecast trends and outcomes based on historical data.

Statistical Testing

Users can perform a range of statistical tests within Tableau, enabling the validation of hypotheses and identification of significant patterns in data.

Clustering Analysis

Tableau supports clustering techniques, aiding in the identification of natural groupings and patterns in datasets.

Implementing Predictive Analytics in Tableau

Tableau's predictive analytics empowers users to forecast future trends and outcomes based on historical data, leveraging predictive modeling algorithms and techniques. Users can create advanced predictive models with ease, facilitating informed decision-making.

Predictive Modeling

Facilitates the creation of predictive models for forecasting.

Trend Analysis

Enables the identification and analysis of trends and patterns.

Performance Forecasting

Supports forecasting future performance metrics and outcomes.

Leveraging Machine Learning Algorithms in Tableau

Tableau's integration with machine learning algorithms empowers users to harness the power of advanced AI and ML capabilities. This enables the development of predictive models, classification algorithms, and anomaly detection for enhanced insights and decision-making.

1

Predictive Models

Users can build and deploy predictive models to anticipate future outcomes and trends.

2

Classification Techniques

Tableau supports classification algorithms for organizing data into distinct categories or groups based on specific attributes.

3

Anomaly Detection

Machine learning algorithms in Tableau aid in detecting anomalous patterns or outliers within datasets, facilitating proactive identification of potential issues.

Conclusion and Future Trends in Advanced Analytics with Tableau

In conclusion, the integration of advanced analytics and Tableau offers organizations powerful tools to unlock valuable insights from their data, enabling informed decision-making and strategic planning.

As the field of advanced analytics continues to evolve, Tableau is expected to further integrate emerging technologies, such as augmented analytics and natural language processing, to enhance the depth and accessibility of data-driven insights.